

СТРУКТУРА И МНОГОЛЕТНЯЯ ДИНАМИКА
СОРЕВНОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ
ВЫСОКОКВАЛИФИЦИРОВАННЫХ БАСКЕТБОЛИСТОВ

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С.С.Кувондиқов –

*профессор и.о. Кафедра физического воспитания и спорта
Ташкентский государственный педагогический университет
имени Низами*

Аннотация: Данная статья рассматривает соревновательную деятельность баскетбольных команд как систему, компоненты которой поддаются количественной оценке и при условии мониторинга даст возможность оптимизировать данные показатели и спортивные результаты.

Ключевые слова: соревновательная деятельность, система, компоненты системы, эффективность, оптимизация, корреляция.

STRUCTURE AND LONG-TERM DYNAMICS OF COMPETITIVE
ACTIVITY OF HIGHLY QUALIFIED BASKETBALL PLAYERS

S.S.Quvondiqov

*- Named after Nizami Acting Professor of
Tashkent State Pedagogical University*

Annotation.: This article considers the competitive activity of basketball teams as a system whose components can be quantified and, subject to monitoring, will make it possible to optimize these indicators and sports results.

Keywords: competitive activity, system, system components, efficiency, optimization, correlation.

The sum of technical and technical techniques and actions combined by a common goal into a single dynamic system characterizes game sports, in particular basketball. The game is based on the interaction and opposition of the team players among themselves and with the players of the opposing team. Taking the ball away and organizing an offensive requires physical effort and the ability to concentrate and think tactically. This determines the variability of the actions of each individual

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player and teams in the course of competitive activity, that is, between components within a single system. A look at competitive activity as a system in which components function according to certain laws and rules allows us to assess the possibilities of individual game indicators for the overall performance of the team, about the strengths and weaknesses of its preparedness.

Data on the structure of the competitive activity of basketball players at various stages of long-term preparatory work under certain conditions can serve as a guideline for adjusting goals and objectives, for choosing means and methods of training athletes during the year, as well as in the pre-competition period.

To assess the competitive activity of basketball players, it is necessary to fix eighteen indicators.

- With the help of correlation analysis of these indicators, it is possible to identify the features of the structure of competitive activity of a single team and the dynamics of changes in this activity.

- The overall performance of the basketball game, for example, correlates with such quantitative game indicators as:

- технические потери;
- attacking transfers;
- fouls of opponents;
- throws;
- interceptions of the ball;
- block shots;

- picking up the ball on your own and someone else's shields. The data block of game indicators largely determines the success of a single game, as well as performances in competitions as a whole. The assessment is made by comparing these indicators of the competing teams and makes it possible to assess the symmetry or asymmetry of the systems of the competitive process.

The lower the place occupied by the team in the championship, the less statistically reliable correlations between each of the game indicators. This can be explained by the fact that a team in optimal athletic form is a system with a harmonious unity of components. The final criterion for such team coherence is the sports result, which also depends on the technical and technical readiness of individual players and the team as a whole.

Long-term monitoring of these indicators provides grounds for making managerial decisions at various levels: current, stage-by-stage, load adjustment, development of individual physical and psychophysiological qualities of players,

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which leads to the improvement of important components of the system - competitive activity, ensuring optimization of its effectiveness.

So, let's summarize. Game indicators have an impact on the effectiveness of the team's performance in competitions in the long term. These indicators directly and indirectly correlate with each other both with the results of the game and with the results of tournaments. The correlation of these indicators is clearly evident when changing and restructuring the structure of competitive activity at various stages of preparation.

Different indicators have different effects on the final result of the game, as they can be interchangeable and mutually pollinated. Also, this influence depends on the success of the team's performance in competitions.

Quantitative indicators of the listed components of the system of competitive activity of basketball athletes at various stages of preparation depend on the physical form and the level of readiness of the opposing players.

The overall result of the competition and quantitative game indicators as its external manifestation can be provided by various functional systems and physical qualities.

In order to optimize the results of each stage of the competitive period, it is necessary first of all to increase the effectiveness of the competitive process system, that is, the effectiveness of managing the preparation of basketball players as a consistent long-term activity using detailed step-by-step models developed based on monitoring quantitative indicators of the main components of the competitive activity system.

LITERATURE:

1. Портнов, Ю. М. Теоретические и научно-методические основы подготовки квалифицированных спортсменов в игровых видах спорта: автореф. дис. д-ра пед. наук / Ю. М. Портнов. – Москва, 1989. – 51 с.

2. Преображенский, И. Н. О некоторых проблемах в моделировании баскетболиста экстракласса / И. Н. Преображенский, А. Я. Гомельский // Научноспортивный вестник. – 1979. – № 5. – С. 32-34.

3. Стонкус, С. С. Теоретические и методические основы спортивной подготовки баскетболистов: автореф. дис. д-ра пед. наук / Стонкус С. С. – Москва, 1987. – 46 с.

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4. Двоеглазов, В. В. Диагностика соревновательной деятельности и разработка игровых модельных характеристик баскетболистов: автореф. дис. ... канд. пед. наук / В. В. Двоеглазов. – Омск, 1989. – 16 с.

5. Приступа, Е. Н. Модельные характеристики и методика повышения результативности соревновательной деятельности единоборствующих баскетболистов при розыгрыше стандартных положений: автореф. дис. канд. пед. наук / Е. Н. Приступа. – Киев, 1989. – 23 с.

6. Иванков Ч.Т., Литвинов С.А. Технология использования модельно-ситуационных характеристик технических действий восточных единоборств для совершенствования физической подготовки студентов педагогических вузов. // Физическая культура, воспитания образование, тренировка. -2008.- №10.-С.5

7. Иванков Ч.Т., Каргин Н.Н. Физическая культура, как предмет образовательного процесса. // Физическая культура, воспитания образование, тренировка. -2009.- №5.-с.45

8. Иванков Ч.Т. Васильев В.В., Жуков Ю.Ю. Методы образно – ситуационного мышления в технико-тактической подготовке юных спортсменов Печат. Международная научно- практическая конференция, М.: МПУ, 2011 .с.34

9. Иванков Ч.Т. Костин, Г.Д., Арустамян М.В., Желтоухов С.В. «Нейтрализация экстремальных ситуаций в прикладных видах спорта при сочетании физических нагрузок и технической подготовки в тренировке юных спортсменов» ././Теория и практика прикладных и экстремальных видов спорта 2012.-№3. -с.6-9

10. Иванков Ч. Т., Сафошин А.В., Глебин А.В., Белых – Силаев Д.В. Управление физической подготовленностью детей школьного возраста на уроках физической культуры на основе единоборств с учетом индивидуальных особенностей // Ученые записки Университета имени П.Ф. Лесгафта.-2014.-№7(111).-С. 76-80 .

11. Иванков Ч.Т., Стефановский М.В., Литвинов С.А. «Организация и проведение студенческих соревнований, по культивируемым видам спорта». (учебное пособие ГОУ ВПО МГПУ М.2015, с.229 с грифом РАЕ).

12. Иванков Ч. Т., Сафошин А.В., Габбазова А.Я., Мухаметова С.Ч. «Теория, методика и практика физического воспитания» учебное пособие ГОУ ВПО МГПУ М.2015, с.429 с грифом УМО).

13. Иванков Ч.Т., Литвинов С.А. «Технология физического воспитания в высших учебных заведениях». (учебное пособие ГОУ ВПО МГПУ с грифом

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